

Table S1. Characterization of ZVI and Fe₃O₄ NPs. Z-potential as measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) in water. Hydrodynamic size and polydispersity index (Pdl) as measured by DLS in water and FETAX solution. Means \pm SE of 3 replicates.

	ZVI NPs	Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs
ζ -potential (mV)	-12.5 \pm 0,4	+9.4 \pm 0,8
Hydrodynamic diameter (nm) \pm SE (Pdl)		
water	3048,3 \pm 298,5 (0,93)	2373,3 \pm 48,3 (0,90)
FETAX solution	2701,7 \pm 214,9 (0,96)	1417,0 \pm 27,8 (0,46)

Figure S1. Time course of pH values of treatment solutions containing FeCl₃ and FeSO₄ at concentrations of 25 and 100 mg Fe/L over 24 h. Each point represents the mean \pm SEM of three independent assays.

Figure S2. Time course of iron NP sedimentation in FETAX solution over 24 h. Each point represents the mean \pm SEM of three independent assays.